

Regional Scenery - Matchmaking no1

* Indicates required question

1. This form does not contain personal and sensitive data. The responses relate to regional data and will be used for research purposes and potential scientific publications related to synergies based on regional needs on I-US, under the project IS2H4C funded by EC. *

Data will be stored to online sheets. Users can request the data. Data will be available upon publication. Data do not contain sensitive and personal information. Answers are anonymous and refer to regions.

Check all that apply.

I understand and agree to the above

According to D1.2 Data Management Plan/ Informed consent:

All individuals who are taking part in a research under the IS2H4C project will have to provide their informed consent to process their necessary personal data collected for the given project purpose.

2. Name of the Region and Country *

3. 1. Please indicate the most active **waste streams** of your region, in terms of size and activities involved (EWC, up to 4 choices) *

Check all that apply.

- Wastes from exploration, mining, quarrying, physical/chemical treatment of minerals (EWC 1)
- Wastes from agriculture, aquaculture, forestry, hunting/fishing, food preparation and processing (EWC 2)
- Wastes from wood processing, panels, furniture, pulp, paper and cardboard (EWC 3)
- Wastes from the leather, fur and textile industries (EWC 4)
- Wastes from petroleum refining, natural gas purification and coal (EWC 5)
- Wastes from inorganic chemical processes (EWC 6)
- Wastes from organic chemical processes (EWC 7)
- Wastes from the manufacture of coatings, adhesives, printing inks (EWC 8)
- Wastes from the photographic industry (EWC 9)
- Wastes from thermal processes (EWC 10)
- Wastes from chemical surface treatment and coating of metals and other materials; non-ferrous hydro metallurgy (EWC 11)
- Wastes from shaping and physical and mechanical surface treatment of metals and plastics (EWC 12)
- Oil wastes and wastes of liquid fuels (except edible oils, 05 and 12) (EWC 13)
- Waste organic solvents, refrigerants and propellants (except 07 and 08) (EWC 14)
- Waste packaging; wiping cloths, filter, protective clothing not otherwise specified (EWC 15)
- Wastes not otherwise specified in the list (EWC 16)
- Construction and demolition wastes (EWC 17)
- Wastes from human or animal health care (except kitchen and restaurant) (EWC 18)
- Wastes from waste management, off-site waste water treatment/preparation for human consumption and for industrial use (EWC 19)
- Municipal wastes (household waste and similar commercial, industrial and institutional wastes) including separately collected fractions (EWC 20)
21. OTHER: wastewater
22. OTHER: sludge
23. OTHER:electricity
24. OTHER:heating

Regional Questionnaire - Matchmaking no2

4. 2. Please indicate which of the below important **infrastructures** existing in your region (check if any and all that apply)

Check all that apply.

- industrial parks/clusters,
- energy production,
- landfill
- recycle center
- Advanced train, highways
- WWTP

5. 3. Please indicate which of the below are considered **critical** in your region (check if any and all that apply)

Check all that apply.

- energy poverty
- water scarcity
- food waste

6. 4. Please indicate the priorities of the below to your defined regional Strategy *

Please indicate different answers to each row
(e.g. economic Priority A, social Priority B, Environmental Priority C)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Environmental	Economic	Social
Priority A	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Priority B	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Priority C	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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